

Deliverable 2.4

Validation approach for CS data in wildlife monitoring and engagement and communication activities

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CI	Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

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Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AU	Aarhus University
BIODIVA	Association of Conservation Biologists
CS	Citizen Science
CSI(s)	Citizen Science Initiative(s)
CT	Camera trap
D	Deliverable
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
eDNA	Environmental DNA
EUSEA	European Science Engagement Association
FAMNIT	Faculty of Mathematics, Natural Sciences, and Information Technologies
HAS	Lovska Zveza Slovenije (the Hunters Association of Slovenia)
HMD	Hunting management district
K&I	Knowledge and Innovation
M	Month
NGO	Non-governmental organization
SRNA	Spremljanje in Raziskovanje Narave z Aplikacijo (Application for Monitoring and Exploring Nature)
T	Task
UP	University of Primorska
WP	Work Package
ZOTKS	Association for Technical Culture of Slovenia

Summary

The validation of citizen science data is paramount to ensure data quality and reliability. This deliverable aims to show how it is possible to correlate between different sources of data, including data collected through ecological sampling techniques (camera traps) and hunting bag data, to assess the quality of citizen science data.

Research Team, WP advisors, stakeholders, and extended participants

The Research Team:

- Prof. dr. Elena Bužan, University of Primorska (Leader of the CSI and Project Coordinator)
- Prof. dr. Boštjan Pokorny, Faculty for Environmental Protection and Hunting Organisation (Co-leader of the CSI)
- Luka Duniš, University of Primorska (member of the Core Team)
- Minja Krstić, University of Primorska (member of the Core Team)
- Dr. Žiga Velkavrh, University of Primorska (member of the Core Team)
- Doc. dr. Hubert Potočnik, University of Ljubljana (member of the Extended Core Team)
- Izr. Prof. dr. Aleksandra Perčin, University of Zagreb (ethical officer)

Relevant advisors for WP2:

- Dr. Francesca Cagnacci (Fondazione Edmund Mach, Member of the Advisory Board of Step Change)
- Dr. Luca Corlatti (ERSAF Regione Lombardia, external advisor for WP2 and co-author of D2.1)

Stakeholders and extended participants:

- Tilen Bartol (HAS), who assisted in the Research Team in hunter recruitment and engagement
- Klara Kopač (BIODIVA – Society of Conservation Biologists), who will assist with student recruitment and engagement
- Lili Mahne (Notranjska Ecological Centre), who assisted in the Research Team in CS (farmers) recruitment and engagement
- Irena Mrak (Alpine Association of Slovenia), who assisted in with the Research team in CS (nature lovers and photographers) recruitment and engagement

- Matevž Adamič (Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food), assisted in represent the contact point with the Ministry
- Mitja Stregar (Slovenian Forestry Service), assisted in being the contact point regarding the management policy

Validation approach for CS data in wildlife monitoring

This deliverable presents the validation approach of the data obtained by the core team of the University of Primorska (UP) working on the CSI for wildlife monitoring in Slovenia. The aim of the validation approach is to check the reliability of data collected by: i) CS smart device application, ii) camera traps deployed in 2022 and 2023 (presented in D2.3) and iii) collected hunting bag data (hunting bag data refers to records of the number and types of animals harvested by hunters over a specific period and area). In future months, the UP team will start using additional methods for data collection, namely method based on the analysis of eDNA from water bodies. eDNA methods can detect species presence with high sensitivity and specificity, even at low densities. This allows for the detection of rare species that might not be captured by camera traps or observed directly by citizen scientists. Additionally, the UP team will analyse data from the wildlife identification quiz (integrated in the SRNA app) to determine SRNA users' proficiency in identifying species included in the SRNA app.

SRNA app

In this chapter, data collected in the SRNA app from 1st of July 2022 to 31st of December 2023 will be analysed and presented. By the end of December 2023, 1082 citizen scientists registered and signed up to use the SRNA app: 544 hunters and 538 non-hunters. Among hunters, 74 (14%) provided at least one report, while among non-hunters 81 (15%) provided at least one report. A report consists of at least one observation of the same species, made at a particular fixed date, time and location. An observation is the basic unit of SRNA which, besides the actual animal sightings, can also include a secondary sign of an animal presence (e.g., tracks, scat, nest). Through the SRNA app, CSs submitted 1037 reports, with a total of 2326 observations in the analysed time period. Figure 1 shows exact locations of reports – green (blue) circles correspond to hunters' (non-hunters') reports, the sizes of circles correspond to the number of observations per report (larger circle, more observations). Hunters reported 1320 observations, while non-hunters reported 1006 observations. Of the 39 species for which SRNA collects data, 30 have been reported: 26 mammal species (not reported: raccoon dog, American raccoon, Alpine marmot, Eurasian beaver and muskrat) and 4 bird species (not reported: black grouse, hazel grouse, grey partridge and common quail). Table 1 shows for each species the number of observations, separately for hunters and non-hunters.

Figure 1: SRNA reports. HMD stands for hunting management district.

Table 1: Number of observations recorded by the SRNA app, sorted by hunters and non-hunter users.

Species	Hunters	Non-hunters	Total	Percentage of total
Alpine chamois	91	39	130	5.59%
Alpine ibex	0	4	4	0.17%
Beech marten	10	3	13	0.56%
Brown bear	26	8	34	1.46%
Coypu	17	19	36	1.55%
Domestic cat	4	2	6	0.26%
Eurasian badger	19	26	45	1.93%
Eurasian lynx	9	3	12	0.52%
Eurasian otter	8	0	8	0.34%
Eurasian red squirrel	7	14	21	0.90%
European brown hare	67	29	96	4.13%
European edible dormouse	18	0	18	0.77%
European mouflon	38	5	43	1.85%
European polecat	2	0	2	0.09%
European roe deer	567	448	1015	43.64%
European wild cat	3	0	3	0.13%
Fallow deer	18	3	21	0.90%
Golden jackal	54	5	59	2.54%
Grey wolf	15	2	17	0.73%
Least weasel	2	0	2	0.09%
Mountain hare	2	1	3	0.13%
Pine marten	1	3	4	0.17%
Red deer	117	287	404	17.37%
Red fox	63	52	115	4.94%
Stoat	2	1	3	0.13%
Wild boar	152	33	185	7.95%
Common pheasant	2	15	17	0.73%
Rock partridge	1	0	1	0.04%
Rock ptarmigan	2	4	6	0.26%
Western capercaillie	3	0	3	0.13%

In the SRNA app, users are encouraged to upload photos with their reports. This allows the UP team to validate the report by confirming if the species recorded in the SRNA app matches the species shown in the attached photo(s). In total, 196 reports had at least one photo attached: 122 of those reports were made by hunters, and the rest (74) by non-hunters. The most reported species on photos was European roe deer (91 times), followed by red deer (65 times), golden jackal and brown bear (21 times) and Alpine chamois (11 times). Out of all the analysed

observations which included photos, none of them were misidentified. This can be attributed to the fact that most of the reports belonged to easy-to-identify species.

SRNA App upgrade

In June and July of 2023, the SRNA app was upgraded by the UP team based on feedback provided by the app users during workshops. The aim of the upgrade was to enhance the user experience and enable better tracking and analysis of wildlife observations. The app was upgraded to track:

1. Animal presence detection options:

- direct observation
- camera trap
- track/scat

2. Confidence levels for identification:

- Could be anything
- Might have been
- Probably was
- I'm positive

3. Photo display upon clicking a point in the map, integrated in Statistics menu, Figure 2.

Figure 2: Map showing brown bear reports. Dark blue dots indicate reports with photos, light blue dots indicate reports without photos.

“Identification confidence” was included as a second way for validating observations, offering non-hunters the opportunity to select the confidence level of their reports. Since this feature was implemented later in the project, only 187 reports include identification confidence information. Of them, 100 were marked “I’m positive”, 86 were marked “Probably was” and 1

was marked “Probably was”. These results indicate a high level of confidence in the reports by citizen scientists.

Comparison of SRNA with the national database

In Slovenia, regular and systematic monitoring of game species and endangered mammals/birds is required by national legislation. Slovenia is divided into 15 hunting management districts (HMD), Figure 3, which are divided into 423 hunting grounds. All the hunting data collected in these areas are stored in 3 national databases, LISJAK, X-Lov and OSLIS. LISJAK is managed by HAS, X-Lov by the Slovenia Forest Service, and OSLIS by the Slovenian Forestry Institute. The OSLIS database aggregates data from LISJAK and X-Lov, making it the most comprehensive database on wildlife harvesting in Slovenia. OSLIS provides data on 70 species, including all SRNA species, except American raccoon and domestic cat. For the data validation comparison, species not included in OSLIS (i.e., American raccoon, 0 observations; domestic cat, 6 observations in SRNA) and species not included in SRNA were discarded. OSLIS data was obtained for all 15 hunting management districts for the years 2022 and 2023 and compared to SRNA data.

Figure 3 Division of Slovenia in 15 hunting management districts.

The SRNA-OSLIS data similarity was examined with the Jaccard index, which was calculated from species presence/absence 2x2 tables that the UP team constructed for each HMD separately. Jaccard index is a well-known statistic, measuring similarity/diversity between two datasets. This index, whose values range from 0% to 100%, is easy to understand and interpret (the higher the value, the more similar the two datasets) and often used in data science applications. Table 2 shows the Jaccard index for each HMD. The values range from 69% in Primorsko HMD to 100% in five HMD (Pohorsko, Posavsko, Ptujsko Ormoško, Savinjsko Kozjansko and Slovensko Goriško).

Table 2: SRNA-OSLIS comparison

HMD	Number of species reported in SRNA	Jaccard index
Gorenjsko	18	72%
Kamniško Savinjsko	14	71%
Kočevsko Belokranjsko	12	83%
Notranjsko	20	80%
Novomeško	6	83%
Pohorsko	7	100%
Pomursko	7	86%
Posavsko	3	100%
Primorsko	16	69%
Ptujsko Ormoško	6	100%
Savinjsko Kozjansko	15	100%
Slovensko Goriško	3	100%
Triglavsko	8	75%
Zahodno Visoko Kraško	12	92%
Zasavsko	8	88%

The most common species reported in SRNA but not in OSLIS were: the Eurasian red squirrel (spotted in seven HMD), the stoat (in three HMD), the rock ptarmigan, the European wild cat, the Eurasian lynx and the mountain hare (in two HMD). The Eurasian red squirrel and the stoat are very common species that are widespread throughout Slovenia, however records of harvest or roadkill are rarely reported. For the other four species, the difference between SRNA and OSLIS data can be explained with the lack of harvest of these species due to their status and/or rarity.

The high Jaccard indices suggest that citizen scientists reported very similar species to those observed in OSLIS, showing that many harvested species can also be encountered alive in nature. On one hand, this finding can encourage people to visit nature more frequently, in order to increase their chances of seeing species that are relatively harmless to people, such as the European roe deer, the Eurasian squirrel or the coypu. On the other hand, this finding reveals which places should be avoided (especially at night) in order to avoid more dangerous species, such as the brown bear or wild boar. In conclusion, in most HMDs there are at least some differences in species reports, indicating that in order to get a better picture about wildlife in Slovenia SRNA and OSLIS databases should be used as substitutes, not complements.

Comparison of SRNA with camera trapping data

To validate the data collected by citizen scientists the UP team compared it to the data collected by our camera traps.

To determine whether there is association between reported species and type of observation (SRNA vs. Camera trap) team performed Fisher's exact test with the corresponding null hypothesis, **that there is no association between them.**

The UP team focused our comparison on the Primorsko hunting management district and three hunting grounds in which team deployed camera traps in 2022 and 2023, Figure 4.

Figure 4: Map of Slovenia showing the area for comparison of SRNA reports (Primorsko HMD, orange border) and camera trap data gathered in three hunting grounds, Rižana, Vrhe-Vrabče and Žabnik-Obrov.

In total, 325 observations were reported in the SRNA app for the Primorsko HMD, and 6240 observations were recorded by camera traps, Table 3. CS reported 15 different species; the most common was the wild boar (78, 24%), followed by European roe deer (69, 21%). With camera traps we recorded 22 mammal species and 13 bird species, however none of the recorded bird species were collected by the SRNA. Out of the 15 species recorded by CS, three were not recorded by camera traps (coyote, grey wolf, rock partridge).

Table 3: Number of species recorded by CS in the SRNA app and by deployed camera traps in three hunting grounds.

Species	SRNA observations	Camera trap observations
Wild boar	78	2160
European roe deer	69	1948
Golden jackal	47	313
Red deer	43	697
Brown bear	18	1
Coypu	13	0
Red fox	12	479
Eurasian lynx	9	1
Grey wolf	9	0
Alpine chamois	8	1
Eurasian badger	7	293
European brown hare	7	205
Eurasian red squirrel	2	31
Cats	2	111
Rock partridge	1	0

The Fisher's exact test suggests that reported species and type of observation are statistically significantly associated ($p < 0.05$), which in our case means that for some species, the SRNA provides different information than the camera trap data. The main reason for this result are the observations of brown bear, the coypu, the Eurasian lynx, the grey wolf, and the Alpine chamois, which were much more frequently reported by SRNA users than captured by our camera traps. A possible reason is the fact that camera traps were set up in fixed locations for a certain period, while citizen scientists were free to explore the area throughout the observation period.

Wildlife identification quiz

In the following chapter, the results of the quiz will be presented, taken by the SRNA app users in the first 18 months of the application's operation, namely in the period from July 1st, 2022 to December 31st, 2023.

Performance metrics

The performance of respondents in the wildlife identification quiz was measured with various performance metrics, which are standard in machine learning to evaluate the classification performance of algorithms (Sokolova & Lapalme, 2009, Kocher & Kumar, 2021, and Chadaga et al., 2023, among others). Accuracy and Kappa metrics measure how good are respondents at identifying animals from a certain mammal group (e.g., Canidae). Accuracy is the percentage of correctly identified animals and its values range from 0% to 100%. Kappa relies on Accuracy but is more complex and useful for imbalanced datasets since, unlike Accuracy, compensates for correct identification that occurs by chance. Its values range from -1 to 1, with a value of 0 indicating that respondents' identification is no better (or worse) than random guessing. In contrast to Accuracy and Kappa metrics, Sensitivity and PPV metrics focus on species within each mammal group (e.g., the red fox, the golden jackal, the grey wolf), and measure the species identification accuracy and reliability of species reports, respectively. In particular, Sensitivity is the percentage of animals of species X that are correctly identified, whereas PPV is the percentage of species X reports that are correct. The values of both range from 0% to 100%. PPV is relevant because in practice researchers only receive reports of an animal - they do not see the actual animal, unless the report is supplemented with a photo. All performance metrics were calculated based on confusion matrices that were created for each mammal group separately. They are available upon request.

General information and demographics

In the studied period, SRNA users solved in total 152 quizzes (additional 16 quizzes were excluded from the analysis because they were only partially solved). Males solved 53% of the quizzes, females 41% (2% of respondents preferred not to say their gender, 2% did not answer the gender question, and 1% chose response "Other"). The analysis revealed that 27% of respondents were aged between 18–25 years, 24% were 26–35 years, 24% were 36–45 years, 10% were 46–55 years, 7% were 56–65 years, and 4% were between the ages of 66–75 years (4% did not answer the question). Around two-thirds of respondents said that prior to

registration in SRNA they had never used a mobile app (like iNaturalist) for recording the presence of animal or plant species.

Most of our respondents (56%) attained a bachelor's degree or completed college. Around one-third (34%) of respondents completed secondary education, 7% reported other level of education, while 3% did not answer the question. Among those 63% (56%+7%) with a university degree, 38% graduated in biology, 18% in agriculture or forestry, 3% in veterinary sciences or husbandry, and 38% in some other field (4% did not answer). The respondents' demographics show that SRNA community is very heterogeneous, which is advantageous for external validity and generalizability of the quiz results.

Wildlife identification

The main task of the quiz was to identify the species of the animal that was present in a featured image. Species were grouped into five mammal groups based on their perceived animal group:

- 1) Canidae,
- 2) the Eurasian beaver and the coypu group,
- 3) Mustelidae,
- 4) the goat-like ungulates, and
- 5) the deer group.

Napaka! Vira sklicevanja ni bilo mogoče najti. shows the performance metrics (Accuracy, Kappa) for our mammal groups, while Figure 6 shows the performance metrics (Sensitivity, PPV) for particular species within each mammal group.

Animals from the Eurasian beaver and the coypu group were the animal types that were successfully identified the most, namely in 87% of cases (Kappa value was 0.74). Identification of animals from the deer group, the goat-like ungulates group and the Canidae family was also fairly successful, with Accuracy ranging from 75% to 78%, and Kappa ranging from 0.63 to 0.67. Identification of animals from the Mustelidae family proved to be very challenging for the respondents, as only 59% of all identifications were correct. Nevertheless, even mustelids identification was much better than random guessing, as evidenced by the Kappa value of 0.49.

Figure 5: Performance metrics – Five mammal groups. Accuracy is plotted with respect to the primary (left) axis. Kappa is plotted with respect to the secondary (right) axis.

The UP team proceeded the analysis of the quiz data by calculating Sensitivity and PPV metrics. With these two metrics the team investigated the performance of respondents on the *species* level, which showed which species within each mammal group are easier/harder to identify. Most respondents had no problems distinguishing the Eurasian beaver from the coypu. The Eurasian beavers were correctly identified in 92% of cases, while coypus in 83% of cases. The coypu reports were more reliable than the European beaver reports though, as evidenced by the PPV values (94% vs. 83%).

In the quiz, photos with deer species show only females, since males are expected to be easily distinguished. When seeing a photo with a deer, most respondents did not have problems identifying the European roe deer – they were correctly identified in 88% of cases. While the identification of the fallow deer females was also fairly successful (Sensitivity: 76%), the identification of the red deer females was less successful. They were correctly identified in 66% of cases and were most frequently mistaken for the European roe deer (this calculation is based on confusion matrix which is available upon request). In addition, the calculation of PPV revealed that reports of the fallow deer were much more reliable than reports of the other two deer species, which had a PPV of 76% (PPV of the fallow deer was 86%).

For the three goat-like ungulates, the Alpine chamois was correctly identified in 90% of cases. The identification of Alpine ibex was less accurate (Sensitivity: 74%), but still relatively high compared to identification accuracy of feral goats (and some other mammals included in the quiz). Feral goats were misidentified in 42% of cases, with the majority (81%) of misidentified feral goats misidentified as Alpine ibex. The reverse misidentification occurred much less often. In particular, 48% of misclassified Alpine ibex were misclassified as the feral goat. Regarding the reliability of reports, the reliability of the Alpine ibex and the Alpine chamois reports was high (PPV of 86% and 83%, respectively). In contrast, the reliability of the feral goat reports was low, as PPV did not even reach 50%.

In the Canidae family, the red fox was much easier to identify than the other two species, the golden jackal and the grey wolf. The red fox was correctly identified in 93% of cases, whereas the golden jackal and the grey wolf in 68% and 62% of cases, respectively. The calculation of PPV revealed similar pattern, as the reports of the red fox were much more reliable (PPV: 95%) than that of the golden jackal and grey wolf (PPV of 75% and 68%, respectively).

According to the quiz results, the respondents had the most trouble identifying Mustelidae species - especially the stoat, which was correctly identified in only 35% of cases. The identification accuracy (i.e., Sensitivity) of the least weasel, the beech, and the pine marten was 61%, 60% and 64%, respectively. The stoat was most frequently misidentified as the least weasel, and vice versa. The beech marten was most frequently misidentified as the pine marten, and vice versa. The European polecat had the highest Sensitivity, namely 70%. Among mustelids, it also had the highest PPV (89%), meaning that the reports of the European polecat were more reliable than the reports of the pine marten (PPV: 77%), the beech marten (PPV: 56%), the least weasel (PPV: 44%) and the stoat (PPV: 43%). The PPVs of the last two species were below 50%, indicating that a researcher should be very cautious when dealing with the actual reports of the least weasel or the stoat.

Figure 6: Performance metrics - species within mammal groups.

Based on the analysed data provided in this document, it is clear that citizen science data provides a valuable source of information that complements the data collected via other more conventional methods. By comparing CS data with data collected with established methodologies, like camera traps and hunting bag data, it has been shown there is a high degree of similarity between the species observed by citizen scientists and species captured by camera traps or harvested by hunters (OSLIS data). By analysing the wildlife identification quiz, it has shown that citizen scientists are rather good at identifying wildlife species (except non-mustelids). However, it is still very important to engage the community through feedback and training to ensure the participants are educated, thus contributing significantly to conservation efforts. The use of confidence levels, and comparisons with national databases underscores the effectiveness of the SRNA app and citizen science contributions in monitoring biodiversity. This

validation not only confirms the data's reliability but also highlights the potential of citizen science in complementing traditional wildlife monitoring techniques, thereby improving the understanding of Slovenia's wildlife diversity and distribution, especially for rarer species which are not captured by camera traps.

Engagement and communication activities

At the beginning of the project, the UP team identified our stakeholders in order to understand different needs and interests of different target groups.

Figure 7. Stakeholders' identification

At the same time, the UP team developed a carefully tailored communication and dissemination strategy for each identified group. The team have strengthened our promotion, communication and dissemination efforts by using a number of innovative and strategic tools:

- **Social Media Engagement:**
 - The UP team joined several social media platforms to connect with diverse audiences:
 - Instagram: @molecularecolup
 - Twitter: @MolecularEcolUP
 - Facebook: Molecular Ecology UP
 - LinkedIn: Molecular Ecology UP.

The social media platforms of the WP2 core team were linked to the original Step Change project's social media platforms.

- **Marketing Materials:**
 - A roll-up banner was designed and produced to visually communicate our research.
 - A coherent set of PowerPoint templates and leaflets was created to facilitate consistent presentations and information distribution.

- **Brand Identity:**
 - Our project logo and design template were created in accordance with the Step Change branding guidelines, ensuring a unified and professional appearance across various mediums.
- **Instructional Video:**
 - A promotional video titled "How to Install and Use the SRNA App" was produced to provide straightforward, visual guidance to users.
- **Ongoing Update of Promotional Materials:**
 - To ensure that our promotional materials remain up-to-date and relevant, the team commit to regularly review and update them. This includes refreshing the content on our social media platforms, revising our PowerPoint templates and leaflets, and potentially creating new promotional videos to reflect the most recent advancements and updates in our projects and research. Our dedication to maintain updated promotional materials ensures that our communication and dissemination strategies always reflect our latest work and achievements.

Figure 8. Promotion material

The promotional campaign was co-designed by the core team of WP2 and the offices for public relationships (PR) of HAS and UP. The promotion campaign was also supported by the Communications and Dissemination Officer Chris Styles from EUSEA and the Science to Policy Specialist Carla Perucca Iannitelli from Science for Change.

The promotional campaign (offline and online) began in March 2022 and was targeted towards the participants of the HAS, Student Council of the University of Primorska, Notranjska Ecological Centre (NGO), Alpine Association of Slovenia (NGO), Association of Young Farmers in Slovenia (NGO), Biodiva (NGO), Scout Association (NGO), Fishermen's Association of Slovenia (NGO), Association Dinaricum (NGO), Ministry of the Environment and Spatial Planning, Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food, Slovenian Forestry Service, TV Studio, RTV Slovenia.

Initially, promotions of the Step Change project, particularly the SRNA app, were made on radio podcasts, TV shows, and social media platforms. The core team leader of WP2 and Step Change coordinator, prof. dr. Elena Bužan spoke about the importance of monitoring wildlife through the SRNA app and the importance of citizen science. Citizen scientists can contribute valuable (meta)data and thus help researchers to make more accurate estimations about species distributions, abundances and their status. Such knowledge will potentially lead to the development of conservation and management strategies enabling a harmonious coexistence of all species.

- **Radio podcasts:**

- RTV Slovenija (PRVI) – Prof. Dr. Elena Bužan: Environmental changes are now so rapid that many species cannot adapt to them.

RTV SLO RADIO TELEVIZIJA RTV 365 SPORED VEČ O RTV IŠČI

PRVI SPORED PODKASTI EKIPA FREKVENCE KONTAKT

29. 4. 2022 33 min

Elena Bužan: Spremembe v okolju so danes tako hitre, da se jim številne vrste ne zmorejo prilagoditi

O molekularni ekologiji s prof. dr. Eleno Bužan.

Naglo upadanje biotske pestrosti je eden najbolj perečih problemov sodobnega sveta. Strokovnjaki že govorijo o šestem množičnem izumiranju, pri čemer je nujno imeti pred očmi, da je prejšnjih pet povsem spremenilo vrstno strukturo življenja na Zemlji. A še mnogo preden vrste dejansko izginejo z obličja Zemlje, se zmanjša njihovo število in, kar je še pomembneje, njihova genska variabilnost, ki zagotavlja večjo odpornost na pretrese, ki jih povzročijo spremembe v okolju.

“Vrste z veliko genetsko variabilnostjo so namreč bolj odporne na spremembe in šoke. »Tudi če samo nekaj osebkov preživi, bodo ti imeli zadosten genetski sklad, da se bo populacija lahko obnovila. Če pa je genetska variabilnost vrste majhna, to prispeva k temu, da vrste izgubijo možnost prilagajanja na spremembe v okolju,« je izpostavila **prof. dr. Elena Bužan** s Fakultete za matematiko, naravoslovje in informacijske tehnologije Univerze na Primorskem ter Fakultete za varstvo okolja iz Velenja.

Danes so spremembe tako hitre, da se marsikatera vrsta ne uspe prilagoditi. Poznavanje genske raznovrstnosti današnjih vrst je zato toliko pomembnejše, saj ponuja orodje tudi za njihovo učinkovitejše ohranjanje. Preučuje se tako redke in ogrožene vrste, ki so na robu izumrtja, kot tudi zelo pogoste, kot je denimo pri nas srna, ki pa ima ključno vlogo v ekosistemu.

Zanimiv vpogled v procese prilagajanja na spreminjajoče se okolje pa prinašajo raziskave, ki skušajo razbrati, kako so se te prilagoditve vpisovale v genski zapis vrste skozi dolgo obdobje 20 000 let, kot so konkretno raziskovali pri gamsih.

Nina Slaček

Podobe znanja

Vse epizode Naroči se

922 epizod

Podobe znanja so razpoznavna tedenska oddaja Programa ARS nacionalnega Radia. V formi polurnega portretnega intervjuja predstavljamo ugledne slovenske intelektualce in znanstvenike vseh generacij in z vseh področij humanistike, družboslovja in eksaktnih

Figure 9. Radio podcast - RTV Slovenija (PRVI)

- TV Slovenija (Radio Koper) – Prof. Dr. Elena Bužan: SRNA: New wildlife monitoring app

A. Š.
21. julij 2022 ob 13:06
Koper - Radio Koper

SRNA: nova aplikacija za spremljanje prostoživečih živali

Aplikacija omogoča tudi neposredno komunikacijo z raziskovalci

Vnosi opažanj živali bodo omogočili izboljšanje poznavanja, posledično pa tudi upravljanja in varstva prostoživečih živali v Sloveniji.

Z beleženjem opažanja redkih ali ogroženih kot tudi pogostih vrst lahko vsak od nas prispeva k izboljšanju poznavanja njihove razširjenosti in številčnosti, kar bo omogočalo raziskovalcem boljše ocenjevanje njihovih gostot ter splošno v kakšnem stanju so vrste. Pridobljeno znanje bo prispevalo tudi k izboljšanju varstva in upravljanja vrst oz. zagotovilo harmonično ravnovesje obstoja vrst. O tem se je **Boštjan Simčič** pogovarjal z **dr. Elena Bužan**, vodjo projekta in predstojnico Oddelka za biodiverzitetu na UP Farnit.

Zadnje iz sekcije

- Barvni frazemi: črna
- Aleksov čudoviti um
- Kako in kje se lahko povežeta znanost in umetnost?
- Oživele lutke iz Maljine skrinjice
- Barvni frazemi: zelena barva

Več informacij o aplikaciji najdete [tukaj](#).

Figure 10. Radio podcast – RTV Slovenija (Radio Koper)

- **TV shows:**

- Planet »Jutro na Planetu« – prof. dr. Elena Bužan and prof. dr. Boštjan Pokorny

Figure 11. TV show – Jutro na Planetu

- **National news**

- The role of the SRNA app was presented and promoted to the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, and Food by prof. dr. Elena Bužan, prof. dr. Boštjan Pokorny, and doc. dr. Hubert Potočnik.

Vodstvo LZS z državnim sekretarjem Krajčičem o aktualnih temah s področja lovstva

21. 10. 2022

Vodstvo Lovske zveze Slovenije se je včeraj sestalo s predstavniki Ministrstva za kmetijstvo, gozdarstvo in prehrano, z državnim sekretarjem dr. Darijem Krajčičem na čelu.

Vodstvo LZS in predstavniki SZS LZS na sestanku z državnim sekretarjem MKGP dr. Krajčičem. Foto: Urša Kmetec

Figure 12. National news - HAS leadership with State Secretary Krajčič on topical issues in the field of hunting

- Newspapers
 - "Naš čas" – prof. dr. Elena Bužan: Be Explorers - Monitor animals in the Šaleška Valley.

Figure 13. Newspaper – "Naš čas"

- **YouTube:**

- HAS "Dober pogled"- prof. dr. Elena Bužan and Luka Duniš

oddaja Dober pogled, februar 2023

Lovska Zveza Slovenije
469 naročnikov

Naročite se

Figure 14. HAS series – “Dober pogled”

- **Website news**

- Študent - SRNA: New wildlife monitoring app

Figure 15. Študent website news

- HAS - SRNA: a new app for recording sightings of game and other wildlife species

SRNA: nova aplikacija za beleženje opažanj divjadi in drugih vrst prostoživečih živali

18. 7. 2022

Za lažji in bolj sistematičen monitoring izbranih vrst prostoživečih živali (predvsem divjadi) smo v sodelovanju Lovske zveze Slovenije in treh raziskovalnih inštitucij (Univerze na Primorskem, Univerze v Ljubljani in Fakultete za varstvo okolja iz Velenja) razvili aplikacijo z imenom SRNA (Spremljanje in Raziskovanje Narave z Aplikacijo).

Foto: Matic Vožič

Figure 16. HAS website news

- UP FAMNIT (News) – Minja Krstić: Promoting the Step Change project and SRNA app in an interview for International Day of Women and Girls in Science.

Minja: *We've been fascinated by science since we were kids.*

Aja: *As part of our studies in Conservation Biology and Nature Conservation, we knew that we had to acquire additional competences alongside our studies. During our studies, we were actively involved in various student-funded projects, such as the "On the creative path to knowledge". Minja: So here we are today: two women in science working in the field of molecular ecology at the*

University of Primorska.

Aja: *For us researchers, science is much more than just a job; it is our mission and our joy. Minja: If you also enjoy science, help researchers to obtain data on Slovenia's wildlife. As part of the Step Change project, we have developed the SRNA app, which allows all of you citizen scientists to help researchers collect data and monitor the status of Slovenia's wildlife.*

Aja: *Through this link, you too can become citizen scientists!*

Aja Bončina, researcher at the Department of Biodiversity, UP FAMNIT (left in the picture) | Minja Krstič, researcher at the Department of Biodiversity, UP FAMNIT (right in the picture)

Figure 17. FAMNIT website news

• Journals

In September 2022, the SRNA app was mentioned twice in the journal "Lovec".

SRNA: nova aplikacija za beleženje opaženih divjadi in drugih vrst prostoživečih živali

Monitoring (spremljanje stanja) populacij prostoživečih živali se glode na to, ali so vrstičene med lovske vrste (to je divjadi) ali zavarovane, je mnenj del sodobnega varstva in ali trajnostnega upravljanja populacij. Sistematičen monitoring omogoča vrst je potreben tudi zaradi obveznosti, ki izhajajo iz slovenske in evropske zakonodaje.

Za lažji in bolj sistematičen monitoring izbranih vrst prostoživečih živali (predvsem divjadi) smo v sodelovanju Lovske zveze Slovenije in vseh nazi-skovanih institucij (Univerze na Primorskem, Univerze v Ljubljani in Fakultete za varstvo okolja iz Velenja) razvili aplikacijo z imenom SRNA (Spremljanje in Raziskovanje Narave z Aplikacijo). Vsi zainteresirani z aplikacijo lahko beležijo opazanja divjadi na terenu, zanimivosti pri uplenjenih živalih in zbirate pomembne podatke o njihovem zdravstvenem stanju ter razmnoževalnem potencialu.

Zbrani podatki bodo omogočili izboljšanje poznavanja, posledično pa tudi upravljanja in varstva prostoživečih živali (velikih sesalcev in izbranih vrst ptic) v Sloveniji.

Lovci ste smo najboljši poznavalci divjadi in mnogih drugih vrst prostoživečih živali, pri svojih izločkih v lovskih pa dnevno opazujemo različne zanimivosti in pridobivamo številne podatke.

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LOVSKA ORGANIZACIJA

Le-te pogosto tudi beležimo, a praviloma ostajajo zgolj kot zapiski v lastnih arhivih in sponkarsko pa sistematično zbirani in obdelani. Prvi zaradi sistematičnega zbiranja in razpršenosti delne podatke povežemo med sabo, jih ustrezno statistično obdelajo in analizirajo, je mogoče pridobiti nove pomembne informacije, ki so izjemnega pomena tudi za izboljšanje upravljalnega procesa.

predativnikov koočenogih kur) bomo lovci bistveno izboljšali pomnvanje njihove razširjenosti, populacijskega stanja in trendov, s čimer bomo pomembno pripelvali tudi k varstvu teh vrst ter tako utrdili našo naravovarstveno poslanstvo.

Lovci lahko do aplikacije dostopajo prek pametnega telefona ali računalnika z lastno identifikacijsko kartico, napisano na lovski izkaznici. Uporaba aplikacije je kličn-tem kompleksnosti (omogočeni so nes številni vnosi različnih opazanj) preprosta, saj nas od začetka do konca vnosa vodi notranje povezave in pregledni meni. Z uporabo aplikacije je mogoče poleg različnih vnosov opazanj slediti tudi statistiki vnosov (lastnih in na območju države). V aplikaciji je tudi možnost nalaganja fotografij iz vaših fotokamer. Zelo bomo vesel, če boste pripravljeni z nami delati vaše podatke.

Aplikacija je namenjena tudi napovedni komunikaciji med lovci in raziskovalci, saj lahko prek nje poročujete kakršnakoli vprašanja o povezavi z valnimi opazaji oziroma divjadi nasploh na naslov: stepchange@famnit.si.

O rezultatih vas bomo redno obveščali. Posameznike z največ vnosi bomo za sodelovanje in še lažje beleženje podatkov o prostoživečih živalih nagradili s sodobnimi lovskimi kancerami.

Vahimo vas, da aplikacijo čim prej preizkusite, na primer ob čakanju divjadi na preči, in jo uporabljate čim pogosteje.

Elena Bužan

Aplikacija SRNA - vnos opažene živali

so bili v preteklosti v znanstvenih krogih podatki, pridobljeni z neposrednim opazovanjem, pogosto zamenjavani oziroma celo podcenjeni. Vendar so z novimi tehnološkimi metodami povzročila navedena opazovanja navedena opazovanja navedena opazovanja (v tem primeru lovcev) in sistematične analize ter njihove njihove sinerže uspešnejših raziskovalcev izjemna opazanja zopet postala izjemno pomembna, lovci pa postajajo izjemno pomembni objektivni znanstveniki (angl. citizen scientists). Le s sodelovanjem lovcev kot izjemno dragocenih lovskih sodelavcev in raziskovalcev, ki lahko zbrane

Figure 18. Journal »Lovec« - September 2022 – Prof. Dr. Elena Bužan

Delovanje komisij in delovnih teles Upravnega odbora LZS

Mag. Aleš Klemenc, predsednik LZS

Ena izmed glavnih nalog Lovske zveze Slovenije (LZS) je povečevanje slovenskih lovčev in lovcov pri skupnem cilju varstva narave in okolja ter trajnostnem upravljanju s divjadi in uravnavanju lovskih virov. LZS je samostojna lovška in naravovarstvena nevladna organizacija, ki deluje v javnem interesu s 115-letno tradicijo in je strokovno ter etično interesno zavezana za 117 lovcev, od katerih je 585 lovčev. Za aktivno sodelovanje s dragimi nevladnimi organizacijami je podpisala posodne dogovore in sporazume o sodelovanju, in sicer s Kinološko zvezo Slovenije, Ribičsko zvezo Slovenije, Gasilsko zvezo Slovenije, Turistično zvezo Slovenije, Čebelarstvo zvezo Slovenije, Ptariško zvezo Slovenije ter Društvo o sodelovanju s Obovratno šolo Daljina Mamina in Triglavskim narodnim parkom. Skupaj s Ribičsko zvezo Slovenije, Ptariško zvezo Slovenije in Zvezo tabornikov Slovenije deluje v Vrhuški skupini za obliko in izvedbo zakonodajne in znanstvenih sprememb na področju zakonodaje.

Za učinkovito doseganje ciljev so poglavitni strokovnjaki, upravljanje znanstvenih izhodov, pridruženje in vedno ravnajo ter v prihodnost naravnano delovanje vseh 15 komisij in delovnih teles Upravnega odbora (UO) LZS. LZS je transparentna in učinkovita v svojem delovanju in vse bolj izrazito prepovedna ter upoštevna v očeh javnosti kot odgovorna naravovarstvena organizacija in pomemben partner na področju lovsko-upravnega načrtovanja. To se odraža tudi v upoštevanju večine predlog in priporočil LZS v javni razpravi o osnutku godišnjegospodarskih in lovskopravilnih ukrepih za obdobje 2021-2028.

Lani in v začetku letošnjega leta je bilo učinkovito ter sistemsko delo komisij in delovnih teles UO LZS organizirano v okviru časovnih okrepov za zmanjšanje tveganja okužbe ter preprečevanje širjenja nalezljive bolezni covid-19. Glavina sej je potekala videokonferenčno prek aplikacije Microsoft Teams in dopisnih sej. Tako je bil na dopisni seji koordinacije predsednikov komisij, Strokovno-znanstvenega sveta, predsednika Uredniškega odbora glasila Lovca, Zlatorogov in Spokorne kobilice ter celotne strani LZS v oktobru 2021 soglasno sprejet usklajen predlog 15delovnih teles Upravnega odbora LZS za leto 2022. Kljub temu je sprejel Upravni odbor LZS na seji novembra 2021. Z njim so bili seznanjeni vsi člani članic na delnih občinskih zborih LZS in samem občinskem zboru LZS v juniju 2022.

V postopku sprejemanja Vsebinskega in finančnega načrta LZS za leto 2022 so izdelali in upoštevali tudi še vsaj 12 % trend zmanjševanja članstva v zadnjih petih letih in dejstvo, da se vsilna letna članarina ne spreminja in ostaja 55 evrov. Prva pilotna finančna načrta za leto 2022 je tudi namenilo pričetka gradnje Nacionalnega lovškega centra Zlatorog. Naloga

LZS je, da z zbiranimi sredstvi upravlja skrajno racionalno in gospodarno ter učinkovito izpelje vsaj več predloženih vsebin in programov. Zagotovljena so transparentna in obsežna merila za delitev sredstev pri izbiri usposobljenih članic za izvedbo razpisov skupnih nalog iz programov dela posameznih komisij po Pravilniku o financiranju določenih skupnih nalog članic LZS. Razpisi so praviloma objavljeni čim prej v začetku tekočega leta.

Komisija za lovsko kulturo in odnose z javnostmi uspešno nastopajo in izvajajo novo organizacijsko shemo Priznanih lovskih kultur, v okviru katerega bo postalo leto 2022. Seznam lovskih pevskih zborov in registri, ki bo letos v začetku septembra skupaj z Dnevi lovškega srečanja Pragersko 2022. Komisija se izdeluje jubilejnih nastopov in koncertov lovskih kulturnih skupin, nudi finančno pomoč za odmerne nastope skupin, izvaja izobraževanje in strokovna usposabljanja na osnovi javnega razpisa prek usposobljenih članic, organizira delovno prevereno v opoznanju letnega rakanja in izdelajo ekipe na evropskem preveritvi v opoznanju letnega rakanja. Člani ekipe so na 23. Evropskem preveritvi v opoznanju letnega rakanja od 18. do 12. junija zaseli peto in šesto mesto, ekipa pa se je uvrstila na četrto. Najboljše za otroke Dobri dan v letovanju 18. junij v juniju je skupaj s Komisijo Mladi in lovcem ter lovcem Lovske družine (LD) Mengeš in LD Kamnik. Lovskim pevskim zborom Medole, Domžalskim registri ter opoznanju letnega rakanja izvedla odmerne predstave in promocijo lovstva.

Komisija za izobraževanje skrbi za enoten način pri izobraževanju lovskih pripravnikov, vzpodbuja obhiti Tehniškega muzeja in biološke učilnice v Metu na Soči, zagotavlja učna gradiva, ki jih je izdelala LZS, in sofinancira pomembne izobraževalne prireditve usposobljenih članic. Pripravljen je tudi enoten nabor Preloaga vpravljanj za pitni in ustni del lovskih izpitov.

Komisija za lovsko kinologijo je pripravila predlog prenovljenega Pravilnika o uporabi lovskih psov v lovskih, ki se bo v nadaljnjih ukrepih prijavila. Kljub pripravi Ministrstva za kmetijstvo, gozdarstvo in prehrano, pridruženje si za pomembnejšo vlogo lovške kinologije, prerojo in nadgradnja modula Lovska kinologija in aplikacija Ljaski ter moduli za učinkovito in transparentno razdeljevanje sredstev na podlagi sprejetih določil delne srečanja za izvedbo kinoloških prireditev. V nadaljevanju bo treba postopki nove sheme sodelovanja s Kinološko zvezo Slovenije.

Komisija za lovski informacijski sistem učinkovito in zavezito skrbi za sistemsko izboljšanje uporabnikov informacijskega sistema Ljask na ravni lovskih družin in usposobljenih članic, dopolnjevanje in nadgradnje programske vsebine na podlagi zakonitih navedb in prejetih predlogov komisij ter sprememb interesnih aktov, pomembno sodeluje pri razvoju novih uporabniških aplikacij. Taktično aktivno sodeluje pri postavitvi nove statistične aplikacije Srsu, ki je namenjena boljšemu opazovanju divjadi in drugih vrst prstoživečih živali.

Strokovno-znanstveni svet zagotavlja učinkovito reševanje odprte problematike, delovanje Uredniškega odbora Zlatorogovega žbenika, prenos znanja lovcev – kmetijskim uporabnikom, promocijo in prenos znanja v širšo družbo, predstavljanje izvirnih

Figure 19. Journal »Lovec« - September 2022 – Mag. Aleš Klemenc President of the HAS

In the November 2022 issue of the journal "Lovec"/"Hunter", prof. dr. Boštjan Pokorny explained the term “citizen science” and highlighted why it is important to include Slovenian hunters as citizen scientists. He also introduced the Step Change project and the SRNA app, which is essential for hunters to store field data and manage wildlife sustainably in Slovenia.

Lovci – zelo pomembni »ljubiteljski znanstveniki«

Prof. dr. Boštjan Pokorny, predsednik Strokovno-znanstvenega sveta LZS

V znanstveno-raziskovalni dejavnosti je (še posebno pri študiju zakonitosti in procesov v naravi) v zadnjih letih vedno bolj popularna in pomembna vključevanje oziroma sodelovanje zainteresirane javnosti. V kontekstu priložnega svadnika imam pri tem v mislih predvsem aktivno sodelovanje pri raziskovanju, na primer s posredovanjem opazujanj in drugih informacij, v nekaterih primerih pa tudi vzorec, ki jih posamezniki pridobijo oziroma čerajo med vsakodnevnimi opravili in predstavljanjem prostega časa v naravi. Takšno aktivno in s strani raziskovalcev delno usmerjeno sodelovanje posameznikov oziroma šiše javnosti v znanstveno-raziskovalnih projektih poznamo v angleškem jeziku kot »citizen science«, za kar se v slovenskem prevodu uporabja izraz ljubiteljski znanost oziroma tudi državljanjski znanost, sodelovalci pa so poimenovali ljubiteljski/državljanjski znanstveniki. Njihovo vključevanje v projekte je zelo pomembna nadgradnja in oplemenitenje znanstveno-raziskovalnega procesa, saj je tako mogoče zbrati pridobiti bistveno več informacij/zorcev, kot bi jih lahko kadarkoli pridobili sami raziskovalci, kar zagotavlja mnogo večjo zanesljivost in robustnost rezultatov ter argumentov. Hkrati lahko določene skupine ljubiteljskih znanstvenikov, ki so usposobljeni oziroma imajo ustrezne izkušnje in znanje, svoja opazovanja in zbrane informacije tudi kritično ovrednotijo, komentirajo ter nato objavijo razumevanje zbranih podatkov. Vseznalci se sodelovanjem se krepi medsebojno znanje med terenskimi sodelavci in raziskovalci, kar spilja na sprijemanje znanstvenih ugotovitev med končnimi uporabniki. Posebej to mora spoznavanje lažje vključevati v vsakodnevno prakso, na primer v procese monitoringa, varstva in upravljanja populacij divjadi.

Upravljalci lovišč (tudi tistih s posebnim namenom) v Sloveniji v skladu s pogoji javne službe opravljajo številne pomembne naloge s področja trajnostnega gospodarjenja (upravljanja) s divjadi, ki so našteje v 21. členu Zakona o divjadi in lovsstvu. Med njimi so tudi zbiranje podatkov o divjadi in njenih odnosih s življenjskim okoljem po določeni

Prav zato lovci pri nas že desetletja – ne da bi se tega zares zavedali oziroma bi se tako pomenovali – delujemo kot zelo pomembna skupina ljubiteljskih znanstvenikov, ki menegore podatke pridobivamo sistematično, kontinuirano in z vso odgovornostjo. V primerjavi z drugimi skupinami ljubiteljskih znanstvenikov, ki so mnogo bolj razsute glede na predznanje in interese, manj usposobljene in v naravo zabujajo preobremen zaradi privlačnega prostega časa, a brez kakovostnih obveznosti, mnogo bolje poznamo in razumemo življenje narave, živalske vrste (vsaj tiste, ki so divjadi), njihove medsebojne odnose ter procese v ekosistemu. Še več: celoten proces izobraževanja v lovstvu, ki je – opepi, za razliko od velike večine drugih držav – v naši državi zelo kakovosten, poglobljen, dolgotrjen, sistematičen in temelji na ustrezem andrijsko-pedagoškem pristopu, zagotavlja usposobljenost lovcev za sodelovanje v monitoringih in znanstveno-raziskovalnih projektih. Zaradi vsega naštetega smo slovenski lovci precej več kot le kmetijski ljubiteljski znanstveniki, saj v primerjavi z drugimi premoremo zelo pomemben dodatek, to je strokovnost, ki izhaja iz bogatih izkušenj, praktičnih znanj, usposobljenosti in predvsem dolgega poznavanja našega glavnega ciljnega objekta – divjadi.

Prav zato smo bili – opepi brez vsakega pomenovanja za ljubiteljske znanstvenike – slovenski lovci od nekaj drugdeset let (nam, da tudi cenjeni) sodelavci raziskovalcev prstoživečih živali. V sodelovanju s njimi smo, na primer, izvajali monitoringe (stevje) divjega pletina in še klasni sivega medveda, kar smo v zadnjih letih nadgradili z zbiranjem več tisoč vzorcev iztrebkov za genetski monitoring odzema prevec zanesljivo določitev številčnosti ter velike zveri. V letu 2017 smo na območju celotne Slovenije začeli sistematično izvajati monitoring evrazijskega sikala, ki je povzeli zgodnjo stanje populacije in omogočil aktivno upravljanje z vrsto. Z zbiranjem vzorcev smo se vključevali v zanimive raziskovalne projekte/programne in monitoringe, namenjene ugotavljanju zdravstvenega stanja lovskih, izposlovanju izbranih ciljnih vrst (vrjadi, game, poljskega zajca) onesnažilom, pa tudi raznočrvalnega potenciala prstoživečih parkljarjev. Hkrati je LZS prvočasno preprečala pomem centralnega zbiranja podatkov in razvila lovskoinformacijski sistem (Ljask). Zgolj lovišč prstoživečih parkljarjev, ki so z mnogimi arbutnimi in teroskimi podatki navedeni v online dostopnem sistemu, se število bliža milijonu, kar je izredno dragoceno in v svetu edinstvena zakladnica podatkov. Le-te smo v preteklosti že s pridom uporabili za različne analize, s katerimi smo pridobili povsem nove spoznanja o ekologiji

Figure 20. Journal »Lovec« - November 2022

- **Other types of promotions (events, workshops, promotional campaigns)**

European Researchers' Night – September 2022

In September 2022, the European Researchers' Night was held, during which the University of Primorska offered workshops for attendees. Primary school students, alongside WP2 team members, Luka Duniš and Minja Krstić, explored hidden wild animals in the environment, considering the Mediterranean area's ecological traits. A quiz within the SRNA app helped pupils learn to identify Slovenian wildlife.

Figure 21. European Researchers' Night

One of the main target groups of WP2 is Farmers' Associations. In November 2022, the core team of WP2 and Notranjska Ecological Centre (NGO) organised an event for farmers to promote biodiversity conservation on farmland and the implementation of the SRNA app in their daily routine. After the first event, there was a great interest in biodiversity education, so a similar event were organised in April (2023) and in May (2023).

Figure 22. Event for farmers in November

Figure 23. Event for farmers in April

Figure 24. Event for farmers in April

Citizen Scientist of the Month – December 2022

The Citizen Scientist of the Month feature is designed to highlight best practices in engaging citizens in research projects. It aims to showcase the strong connection between researchers and citizen scientists, providing an opportunity for individuals to share their experiences while working on the Step Change project.

The campaign "Citizen Scientist of the Month" – In December 2022 the core team of WP2 spoke to Vedran Prodan, a hunter, conservationist, and Vice President of the HA Koper. Vedran talked about how the hunting community actively helps protect the environment, how it provides valuable data on wildlife abundance and behaviors, and how researchers could better support their role as citizen scientists.

Figure 25. Citizen Scientist of the Month – Vedran Prodan

FAMNIT INFO DAYS

In February 2023 the UP FAMNIT organised the FAMNIT INFO DAYS event, where future students learned more about wildlife protection and monitoring.

Figure 26. FAMNIT INFO DAYS

The National Competition in Biology – March 2023

In March 2023, the core team of WP2, alongside ZOTKS, hosted the National Competition in Biology. The competition brought together 238 high school students that scored the most points in the local competition (at their local schools) that involved in total 1677 high school students.

The students wrote the competition exam on different biology topics. Their mentors and teachers attended a lecture from the core team leader of WP2 and coordinator prof. dr. Elena Bužan, who shared knowledge on innovative teaching methods, focusing on the latest methods of biodiversity monitoring and data collection, as well as information about the Step Change project and the practice of citizen science.

Figure 27. The National Competition in Biology – Presentation on innovative teaching methods, focusing on the latest methods of biodiversity monitoring and data collection

Figure 28. Camera-trap

Hunting and Fishing Day – March 2023

The core team of WP2 made a presentation of the Step Change project and the SRNA app at the Hunting and Fishing Day in Celje, which took place from 17th to 19th March 2023. Prof. dr. Elena Bužan also made a statement for the March episode of the series "Dober pogled".

Figure 29. HAS series – “Dober pogled”

Workshop with UP conservation biology students

For conservation biology students, team members Luka Duniš and Minja Krstić prepared and held a workshop on "Monitoring wildlife using apps" in March 2023. Students had to prepare for the workshop in advance and answer the questions:

- Which web-based wildlife monitoring applications exist in Slovenia and Europe?
- Highlight the advantages and disadvantages of each app and make a comparison between the apps.
- How could the usability of the apps be improved (make at least one suggestion for each app)?
- The introductory session included a presentation of the Step Change project and the importance of involving citizen scientists in research projects, followed by a presentation of the SRNA app.

Below is a run down of the event:

1. Students were divided into small groups (3-4 students per group):
 - Each group had to write on sticky notes at least 3 advantages and at least 3 disadvantages of the SRNA app (15 minutes). Students put sticky notes on the board (advantages on one

side of the board, disadvantages on the other side of the board). After wards the team members, Luka Duniš and Minja Krstić, read and discussed all the pros and cons.

2. Based on all the strengths and weaknesses highlighted, students were asked: How could the SRNA app be improved/updated/updated?
 - Each group wrote at least 3 suggestions on sticky notes to solve the problem (15 minutes). Students put sticky notes on the board. The team read and discussed all the suggestions (Question: How to implement the ideas?). Afterwiche the UP team discussed the most fruitful ideas and how these improvements could be implemented into the app.
3. Prototyping and testing:
 - Development of the ideas gathered at the workshop and testing their potential.

Figure 30. Workshop with conservation biology students

Figure 31. Workshop with conservation biology students

Based on the advantages and disadvantages of the SRNA app and the proposed solutions, the team have drawn up a table showing the solutions to the current problems.

STEP CHANGE WORKSHOP 16.03.2023 SRNA APPLICATION		
PREDNOSTI	SLABOSTI	REŠITVE
Izobraževalno gradivo znotraj aplikacije - detaljen opis živali + slike		
Omogoča preverjanje znanja preko kviza		
Vsebina v slovenščini in angleščini		Navodila za uporabo aplikacije je potrebno namestiti, tako da so na bolj vidnem mestu.
Omogočena uporaba obeh operativnih sistemov: Windows in IOS	Ni aplikacije (AppStore/GoogleStore/PlayStore). Format slabo prilagojen za telefon.	V prihodnosti se lahko aplikacija SRNA naredi kot aplikacija, ki se jo lahko prenese iz AppStore/GoogleStore/PlayStore.
Validnost obstoječih podatkov = Podatki potrjeni s strani raziskovalcev	Zaupljivost podatkom brez naloženega fotodokazila.	Obvezen vnos fotografij, da se lahko vneseni podatki ovrednotijo kot veljavni. (Izjema so lahko samo lovci)
Aplikacija je specializirana za prostoživeče živali s katerimi se lahko trajnostno upravlja	Kako se zna da ena žival ni bila opažena/zabeležena večkrat?	
Omogoča vnos opaženih in poveženih živalih, ter vnos dodatnih komentarjev: zdravstveno stanje, obnašanja...		
Fotografij se lahko naknadno naloži	Onemogočena uporaba app brez interneta.	Da program shrani vnesene podatke in da se lahko kasneje. Ko je internet ponovno dostopen, informacije avtomatsko naložijo.
Dostop do baze podatkov (pregled števila vnesenih opažanj/povozov)	Vneseni podatki niso dostopni vsem uporabnikom. Lahko se dostopa samo do lokacije na zemljevidu.	Prosto dostopna podatkovna baza: na zemljevidu se ob kliku na piko odpre slika in podatki o vnosu živali.
Narejena v sodelovanju z LZS	Ni koordinat, ki bi prikazale točno lokacije kje je bila žival opažena.	Koordinate: omogoča dostop do lokacije telefona.
	Ni omogočeno vnašanje podatkov sledi in iztebkov	Omogočanje dodatnega vnosa sledi in iztebkov, ter objava foto gradiva in kviza.
	Enosmerna komunikacija: podatke se nalaga, povratnih informacij se zelo slabo dobi.	
	Pri osebnih vnosi ni vidnih slik - vizualno slabo narejeno	Ko uporabnik vnese slike, se mu kreira za osebni vnos kot fotoalbum z vsemi slikami, ki jih je naložil. Lepši pregled.
Omogoča komunikacijo s raziskovalci.	Ne omogoča enostavno komunikacijo med uporabniki.	Dizajn spletne strani, ki bo omogočala pogovor med uporabniki, kjer si lahko delijo fotografije, videoposnetke, informacije in izkušnje. Lahko se medsebojno posvetujejo, če niso pripricani ali če imajo kakršnokoli vprašanje, preden naložijo podatke v aplikacijo (na ta način bi se zmanjšale napake pri vnosi).
		Motiviranje uporabnikov, tako da se skupljajo točke pri vnosi (prednost imajo tisti, ki vnašajo tudi fotografije ali posnetke). Na koncu leta pa se naredi presek in se lahko uporabniku z največ vnosi dodeli nagrada.

Figure 32. Workshop with conservation biology students – Table of the solutions

Some of the key observations from this website are detailed below:

- Place the instructions for using the app in a more visible position.
- Save the data entered when the internet is restored; automatically upload the information.
- Require photo input to validate entered data (only hunters can be exempted).

- Make the database freely accessible: clicking on the dot on the map opens the image and animal entry data.
- Allow additional entry of tracks and faeces; publish photo material and quizzes for identification.
- Store uploaded images in the user's photo album that retains all uploaded images.
- Improve and enable communication between users, and between users and researchers.
- Motivate users.

Based on all the suggestions, the app was subsequently upgraded.

Step Change field work days – March 2023

In March 2023, the core team of WP2 together with HAS and faculty FVO, deployed camera traps in the hunting ground Oljka Šmartno ob Paki. Subsequently, they deployed them on several other hunting grounds. For FAMNIT students, fieldwork was organised to teach them how to identify wildlife presence, how to effectively deploy camera traps, and how to use the SRNA app in the field.

Figure 33. Deploying camera traps and fieldwork with students

Citizen Scientist of the Month – April 2023

The campaign "Citizen Scientist of the Month" – In April 2023 the core team of WP2 spoke to Klara Kopač, a conservation biologist, and President of the Association of Conservation Biology Students - BIODIVA. Klara talked about how the BIODIVA Association has been organising Biocamp, a biological camp that allows students to gain experience, learn, acquire new skills about wildlife species and nature conservation, and last but not least, socialize. Also, she spoke about how the student community actively helps protect the environment through different

national-level projects and why she thinks it is important to involve students as citizen scientists in wildlife monitoring.

Figure 34. Citizen Scientist of the Month – Klara Kopač

The Association of Biology Students – April 2023

In April 2023, team members Luka Duniš and Minja Krstić presented the SRNA app and the way it monitors wildlife populations at a meeting with the Association of Biology Students at the University of Ljubljana and explained its importance in light of the coming climate and environmental changes.

Figure 35. Presentation of the app to the Biology Students Association

UP ALUMNI Week event – April 2023

In April 2023, as part of the UP ALUMNI Week event, the core team of WP2 presented lectures and workshops focused on "Innovative Approaches to Biodiversity Monitoring." The event began with an introductory lecture, followed by interactive workshops. In these sessions, students were introduced to cutting-edge monitoring methods, which included tracking the distribution, abundance, and other aspects of wildlife. Tools like the SRNA app and the Biotracker VHF radio receiver were showcased. Additionally, the importance of citizen science in researching and understanding the characteristics of Slovenia's wildlife was emphasized.

Figure 36. Presentation of the app and outdoor workshop on "Alumni Week"

Lectures and workshops – April/May 2023

In April and May 2023, a series of lectures and workshops on wildlife monitoring, the SRNA app, and camera traps were organised for pupils from primary and secondary schools in Slovenia.

Figure 37. Lectures and workshops for primary and secondary schools

Spring Wildlife Challenge – April/May 2023

The Spring Wildlife Challenge was organised from 27th April to 3rd May 2023. The challenge was organised to promote the SRNA app and increase the number of users. The promotion also raised people's awareness of the importance of nature and wildlife conservation.

Figure 38. Promotional poster for the Spring Wildlife Challenge

Roe Deer Infographic – June 2023

In June 2023, the core team of WP2 organised an action to raise awareness about roe deer fawns and promote the SRNA app in the section 'How can you help?'

Figure 39. Raising awareness about roe deer fawns and promoting the SRNA app

Biocamp 012- July 2023

In July 2023, team members Luka Duniš and Minja Krstić attended Biocamp 012, hosted by the BIODIVA. They showcased the SRNA app, camera traps, and introduced the Step Change project to students. For seven days, students utilized the SRNA app for wildlife observation, after which they collaborated with the core team to discuss their findings and results.

Figure 40. Participation in Biocamp and Step Change presentation

Conference and other dissemination events

Between June and September 2023, members of the WP2 core team attended various conferences, seminars, events, and meetings, such as Symposia, the 36th Congress of the International Union of Game Biologists, SymBioSe, the Biological-Psychological Student Conference, to underscore the importance of involving citizen scientists in the Step Change project. Additionally, they highlighted the resilience of the SRNA app and camera trap applications for wildlife monitoring.

Jerebica Senj

Figure 41. Participation in conferences, seminars, events, and meetings

One important meeting attended by prof. dr. Elena Bužan was organised by the Croatian Hunting Association "Jerebica Senj". There she emphasized the importance of modern methods for collecting field data on animal reproduction and health, which are being implemented within the framework of the SRNA app developed in the Step Change project. She also highlighted the crucial role of collaboration between hunters and researchers in wildlife protection and monitoring projects.

Figure 42. Participation in meetings organised by the Croatian Hunting Association "Jerebica Senj"

European Researchers' Night – September 2023

In September 2023, the core team from WP2 once again engaged in Research Night, delivering compelling lectures and conducting workshops for pupils from primary schools. At this event the UP team introduced the pupils to the SRNA app, and challenged the pupils to take part in the species quiz. This allowed the pupils an opportunity to explore and identify a variety of wildlife species indigenous to Slovenia.

Figure 43. European Researchers' Night 2023

Citizen Scientist of the Month- September 2023

The campaign "Citizen Scientist of the Month" – In September 2023, the core team of WP2 spoke to Neda Kranjec, a former biology educator from Slovenia. She taught the students about the importance of nature conservation and biodiversity. Currently, Neda is an active member of the citizen science community, where she works to protect the environment.

Figure 44. Citizen Scientist of the Month – Neda Kranjec

HAS Promotional material – September 2023

In September 2023, promotional material was sent to the 411 HAS families.

Figure 45. SRNA app promotion – HAS

House of Experiments - traditional Researchers' Day – November 2023

On November 2023, the House of Experiments organized the traditional Researchers' Day with the aim of introducing the profession of researcher to both girls and boys, encouraging them to pursue natural sciences more frequently, and showcasing the work of both female and male researchers to the general public. Minja Krstić, a member of the core team of WP2, addressed young researchers, emphasizing the importance of nature conservation and the preservation of wild animal species. She also introduced innovative methods for monitoring wildlife in Slovenia, such as camera traps and the SRNA app.

Figure 46. House of Experiments

Evaluation Workshop – January 2024

On January 2024, the core team of WP2, along with partners from K&I and AU, organized an Evaluation Workshop. Stakeholders from WP2 participated in the first part of the workshop.

Figure 47. Evaluation Workshop

Social Media

Throughout the Step Change Project, the core team of WP2 actively promoted Step Change, the SRNA app and camera traps via social media. In addition, the UP team successfully achieved significant engagement and gathered a diverse number of

followers on various social media platforms including Instagram (551), Facebook (341), Twitter (260) and LinkedIn (58). The UP team consistently shared engaging biology content, interesting facts about wildlife and actively promoted citizen science initiatives, campaigns, events and workshops.

Figure 48. Online promotion

Future communication and dissemination

In the coming period, the WP2 core team will continue to focus on maintaining and expanding the campaign to raise awareness about wildlife in Slovenia.

As part of this effort, the team will continue to organise a range of different campaigns, events, workshops and educational posts on various social media platforms. The aim of these activities is to engage a wider audience and encourage a deeper understanding of the importance of conserving Slovenia's rich biodiversity. Through a multi-faceted approach, the team aims to encourage individuals and communities to actively participate in wildlife conservation and contribute to the long-term sustainability of the region's natural ecosystems